

How to Chat with the History of European Drama. Connecting DraCor with a Large Language Model Using an MCP Server.

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1. Introduction¹

With Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers, introduced by Anthropic (2024), an AI architecture component is gaining attention that holds great potential also for new forms of interaction with humanities resources based on Large Language Models (LLM). Using MCP (Hou et al. 2025), a server is able to "expose executable functionality to clients" (such as Claude Desktop²); these functionalities are

called "tools". "[T]ools are designed to be model-controlled, meaning that tools are exposed from servers to clients with the intention of the AI model being able to automatically invoke them" (Anthropic 2025).

In the following, we report initial insights and first evaluations from prototyping an MCP server for the DraCor API. DraCor (dracor.org) is a research infrastructure implementing the concept of 'Programmable Corpora' for drama studies, providing API-based access to TEI-encoded plays and their metadata across multiple mostly European literary traditions (see Fischer et al. 2019; Börner und Peer 2023; Börner et al. 2025). The DraCor MCP Server (Börner 2025) extends this infrastructure by providing state-of-the-art LLM-mediated access to these resources. The implemented MCP tools wrap the API's endpoints and can be dynamically invoked by LLMs, granting them the capacity to execute API-based operations on DraCor in real time. To date, the potential of such AI architectures for Computational Literary Studies (CLS) has not been explored. In our view, there is a great potential in anchoring work with LLMs in the empirical paradigm of CLS, in establishing natural language based interfaces for digital resources, and in controlling and expanding the knowledge that LLMs can draw on. As an example, we display a chat with Claude Sonnet 4 (with and without access to the DraCor MCP server) about the protagonist of the almost unknown play "Die entführte Dose" (Fig. 1 and 2). With MCP access only, the model is able to – correctly – identify the protagonist.

Fig 1: Non-Agentic LLM (without DraCor MCP)

Fig. 2: Agentic LLM (DraCor MCP-enabled)

2. Implementing the DraCor MCP Server

The DraCor MCP Server is built using the "fastmcp" Python framework³, which offers a straightforward approach to developing tool-based interfaces for LLMs. Each tool is a Python function decorated with `@mcp.tool()`. Docstrings – Python's built-in documentation strings that specify a function's behavior, parameters, and outputs – serve as the primary mechanism for instructing the LLM on tool selection and usage. Here docstrings include a brief functional description of the tool, the specific DraCor API endpoint being wrapped, expected parameters with concrete examples, cross-references to related or alternative tools, and explicit guidance on handling common failure scenarios, such as context length limitations or timeout errors. Currently, our MCP server exposes 47 tools, grouped into six categories (cf. Trilcke et al. 2025):

- **Direct API Endpoint Wrappers:** Provide one-to-one access to DraCor's REST API
- **Helper Tools:** Implement filtering and pagination strategies to mitigate context limitations in LLMs
- **Search and Discovery Tools:** Extend DraCor's basic identifier-based access to support search by author, title, normalized year
- **Administrative Tools:** Enable corpus and play-level data management

- **Documentation Tools:** Make metadata, TEI encoding rules, and system specs programmatically accessible
- **Frontend Integration Tools:** Bridge to the DraCor website

This implementation focuses on the potential of an MCP server as a middleware for interactions with CLS infrastructures. It draws attention to design challenges that will influence future iterations of programmable corpora, such as balancing tool specificity with LLM discoverability and managing access in secure versus open environments.

3. Experimental Setup and Evaluation Summary

To evaluate our DraCor MCP server prototype, we designed 16 prompt-based experiments using Claude Sonnet 4 (Desktop).⁴ We focus on tool categories relevant to autonomous data interaction (API wrappers, helper tools, search/discovery tools). The queries were systematically varied along four aspects:

- Scope
- Domain-specific terminology
- DraCor-specific language
- Canonicity

Examples for the queries we prompted are:

- „What is the number of dramatis personae in Dantons Tod?“
- „How does the gender distribution in Swedish drama change over time?“
- „Who is the protagonist in Die entführte Dose?“

Each experiment was evaluated using four criteria (based on Vongthongsri 2025):

- Correct Answer (task completion)
- Tool Correctness (right tool used)
- Tool-Calling Efficiency (shortest viable processing path)
- Tool-Use Reliability (reproducibility across five trials)

The key findings of our experiments are: 13/16 answers were correct, with most failures due to technical limitations (e.g., metadata files for large corpora exceeding the model's context window, LLM refusal to process batch queries). Tool correctness was high (15/16), but efficiency and reliability varied, especially in complex or large-scale queries. Five repetitions of each query revealed substantial reliability variation: some queries produced consistent results while others yielded correct answers in only one of five attempts, raising concerns about reproducibility. Use of DraCor-specific terms increased performance. No performance gap was observed between canonical and lesser-known texts when the MCP server was used. This has important implications for research on under-studied corpora and marginalized literary traditions, as LLM tool use

does not depend on texts being well-represented in training data.

4. Outlook

An important finding from the experiments is the central role of docstrings as the currently decisive factor in determining the tool competence of an LLM. For our further work, this means that a new methodological paradigm appears to be emerging: "docstring engineering" (Trilcke et al. 2025). In the next steps, we want to go through systematic experimentation with different docstrings and develop best practices for docstring design. We are currently developing automated evaluation methods to systematically test docstring variations and MCP design choices across multiple LLMs (cf. Gao et al. 2025; Liu et al. 2025), enabling large-scale repetitions that better capture variance in tool-use behavior and answer reliability as influenced by different documentation strategies. The aim is to create reliable semantic contracts that facilitate precise and creative tool use while compensating for limitations in LLMs. Ultimately, well-crafted docstrings could be pivotal in empowering non-technical users to leverage agentic systems for computational literary analysis.

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Footnotes

1. Author contributions: **Ingo Börner**: Conceptualization, Software (DraCor MCP Server), Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft; **Peer Trilcke**: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Funding acquisition; **Henny Sluyter-Gäthje**: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing; **Daniil Skorinkin**: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing; **Frank Fischer**: Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing; **Carsten Milling**: Software (DraCor API)

2. <https://claude.ai/download>

3. <https://gofastmcp.com>

4. We conducted single prompt experiments with "Extended Thinking" disabled and "Web Search" enabled in Claude Desktop using "claude-sonnet-4-20250514". After the experiment, Claude was asked with a final prompt to document the chat in a Markdown file. These documentations can be accessed here: https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp-evaluation/tree/main/2025_dhd2026-poster-submission

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